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DIGITAL WATER MARKING

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Abstract

Watermarking is a technique for labeling digital pictures by hiding secret information into the images. Digital Watermarking has emerged as a new area of research in an attempt to prevent illegal copying and duplication. In addition to this, image processing is also added that will allow the user to perform various editing functions.

The objective of this paper is to implement a technique for providing confidentiality and authentication. These mechanisms are provided hiding message or image behind the cover image for secure transmissions and to recover the message image back at the receiver side. This will serve the purpose of disguising the user by hiding the actual data inside the cover image so that even if the transmitted image is intercepted by any unauthorized user, he cannot figure out the actual information. Also the authentication purpose can be solved by this means of watermarking. In this paper I have used the algorithm I have used LSB coding.

Keywords: Modules of watermarking, Text watermarking, Image watermarking, Image processing.

Introduction:

Watermarking has been around for several centuries, in the form of watermarks found initially in plain paper and subsequently in paper bills. However, the field of digital watermarking was only developed during the last 15 years and it is now being used for many different applications. Because of the rapid development of networking and the wide use of personal Computers, people can easily access information

world. The digital data can easily be copied. Therefore, the data protection and copyright issues become more and more important. Authentication and Confidentiality are the main issues that needs to be dealt while transmission of highly sensitive information.

The “Digital Watermarking” provides the functionality of authentication and confidentiality thorough text watermarking and image watermarking methods.

Text watermarking module hides the text behind the cover image and Image watermarking hides the image behind the cover image. They can then be used to transmit and store the data in text and image form and also provide authentication for legal distribution of digital data.

Definition of Problem

Because of the rapid development of networking and the wide use of personal Computers, people can easily access information world. The digital data can easily copy. Therefore, the data protection and copyright issues become more and more important. Authentication and Confidentiality are the main issues that needs to be dealt while transmission of highly sensitive information. Various Encryption techniques are available that allows user to transmit the information securely. However if an illegal user gains access to key then information is longer safe, so a mechanism is required that compensate the drawback of the encryption method.

Armed forces and other defence organisations need to transmit text and often, digital images for various purposes information. Therefore the technique is required to disguise the unauthorized user and to prevent the actual. These must be transmitted securely over the network and also must be preserved in the systems so that the intruder or illegal user is unable to get the actual information.

Theoretical Background

Existing System

The various techniques available for providing confidentiality and authentication are implementing cryptographic algorithms, etc. These allows us to scramble the data. With the pace of time more enhanced techniques are evolving for secure text transmission or storage. However if the encryption key is traced by illegitimate user, then the algorithm will no more be useful. Now a days Visible Watermarking is being used for legal distribution of digital data in order to authenticate the distributor.

Problems with Existing System

The current applications available can be used to transmit data securely by using cryptographic algorithms that allows us to scramble the data so that it can be transformed to unintelligent form. However if the intruder gains the knowledge of cryptographic keys and algorithm used, he can try to decode and thus can recover the actual information since these methods can only scramble the data but can't conceal the existence of data. Further visible watermarks are used for legal distribution of data providing authentication which can be easily forged.

Also there is no such single package application that allows us to perform Invisible watermarking and image processing together.

Proposed System

The problem is that all the three miniature versions of the system, i.e. Text watermarking, Image watermarking and Image processing are very heavy and resource extensive and hence doesn't provide a very efficient solution. Thus a simple solution is that all the functionalities can be combined in one software. My software can provide all the image related solutions in one place providing user with much advantage.

Secondly this system uses invisible watermarking technique that is more resistant to forgery as it conceals the existence of actual data and thus the intruder cannot figure out where to apply his efforts to gain access to actual data. This is because the actual data is hidden and what is visible to him is actually

unimportant and irrelevant The image utility functionality is implemented using the Microsoft Visual Studio.

Advantages of the Proposed System

Advantages of the Proposed System can be categorized into several points -

1. Actual information is hidden and made invisible behind any chosen cover image.
2. If the some light weight editing has to be done in the image then that could be easily done without using any other tool.
3. Digital Watermarking in invisible form can be used to provide – confidentiality, authentication, resistant to eavesdropping and traffic analysis.
4. This software works for both text data and image data.
5. Since all the three works, i.e. editing, text and image watermarking as well as recovery of actual data, are being done at one place, so the time spent in doing it separately is saved.
6. The algorithms used are free of cost so no payment is required to use the software.
7. The software works in the windows so no interface problem arises.
8. This can also be used for verifying the distributor of digital data.

Methodology:

Detail of Software used

Operating System	:	WINDOW XP/VISTA/7
Dot net Framework	:	3.0 or later
Microsoft Visual Studio	:	2008

Modules of water marking: Text watermarking

This module consist of two parts :

Encoding: This allows us to hide the textual data behind the cover image. We are required to browse any cover image and to write the text which is to be hidden. Further we are required to set the password and browse for the location and name of the resulting encoded image.

Decoding: This allow us to browse the encoded image and then when we give the correct password the text will be recovered.

1. Image Watermarking

This module also consist of two parts:

Hide: This allows us to hide the image behind the cover image. First we have to select the key file which is used for providing enhanced security as the presence of same key file is necessary for extracting the message image. This is done so that if intruder gains knowledge about the algorithm he can't access the actual data till he is aware of this key file.

Extract: The encoded image is to be browsed and by selecting appropriate key file we can extract the actual image.

The following fig shows the proposed system for implementation of image watermarking.

Block Diagram for Image Watermarking

Image Processing:

This module implements the features of image processing offered by the project. There are various image processing features available which can edit the original image in several manners. The various image editing functions are –

File – open or save the image or to exit the application.

Edit – for undo and clearing the image.

View – for displaying image information or zooming the image.

Color Editing:

Filter – The filters can be used to on the image. The project incorporates RGB filters which can be applied separately over the image.

Brightness – Can increase or decrease the image brightness as required.

Gamma - Can increase or decrease the image gamma as required.

Contrast - Can increase or decrease the image contrast as required.

Grayscale – Converts the image to a grayscale.

Invert – Can be used to invert the image colors.

Image Editing –

Resize – Can be used to resize the image width by height.

Rotate and Flip – can be used to rotate or flip the image.

Crop – Can be used to crop the image by given size from any pixel location.

Insert – Can be used to inset Text, Image and Shape.

Algorithm Used

LSB Encoding-

A message is hidden in the cover image using LSB(least significant bit) technique. Hiding alters the cover image but the alterations are too slight to see. The process permits recovering the message image later and recovered image matches the original data exactly. This is possible because image contains too much information. Common 8- bit color image have 256 shades of colour. People can distinguish only about 40 shades. The extra shades are useless. This watermarking technology uses the unneeded bits to hide the message image. Watermarking stores the information in the least significant bits hence named LSB algorithm.

The steps involved are:

First the data either image or text is converted into bit-stream and cover image in byte stream.

After that each bytes of cover image is used to store a single bit of data stream in the LSB(Least significant bit) of cover image.

One scenario of this hiding technique can be seen as follows:

Let the message image be of 3 pixels having intensity-

$$\begin{pmatrix} 99(01100011) \\ 103(01100111) \\ 105(01101001) \end{pmatrix}$$

Let the cover image be of 24 pixels having intensity-

$$\begin{pmatrix} 90 & 82 & 88 & 115 & 148 & 155 & 126 & 90 \\ 119 & 103 & 80 & 76 & 99 & 131 & 91 & 43 \\ 164 & 120 & 85 & 63 & 59 & 80 & 120 & 91 \end{pmatrix}$$

Hiding the above 3 pixel image in the cover image of 24 pixels alters the pixel intensity as given below.

$$\begin{pmatrix} 90 & 83 & 89 & 114 & 148 & 154 & 127 & 91 \\ 118 & 103 & 81 & 76 & 98 & 131 & 91 & 43 \\ 164 & 121 & 85 & 62 & 59 & 80 & 120 & 91 \end{pmatrix}$$

Thus we can see the slight changes to cover image after hiding the information. These are imperceptible by human eyes. For eg .the pixel value 99 of message image will require the first row of cover image to be hidden. since one bit is hidden in LSB of 1 pixel so 1 pixel of 8-bit to be hidden requires 8 pixels. The second pixel intensity of 1st row changes to 83 from 82 and similar changes occurs in all LSB positions depending on the value of bit to be hidden.

If the bit to be hidden is 1 the LSB will b 1 else the LSB will be 0.

Conclusion: Digital watermarking holds a significant promise as one of the keys to protecting proprietary digital content in coming years. At its heart is the concept of embedding information inside a digital object such that

The embedded information is inseparably bound to the object

The embedded information describes who may legally distribute the objects , as well as who is the legal owner of the object.

Watermark is hidden in the cover image. This hiding alters the cover image, but alterations are too slight to see. The process permits recovering the watermark later and the recovered watermark is exactly same as original one. This is because in 8-bit images have 256 shades of color, among them some shades are indistinguishable by human eyes. These extra bits or unused bits are used to hide the information.

My result indicates that the proposed approach has the potential for hiding information successfully and thus can be used for various security purposes i.e. authentication and confidentiality.

Managerial Application

By using this application the armed forces, defence organizations and other institutions that want to transmit confidential information in the form of image, can easily hide it inside some other image. This application can also be used by common people to hide their pictures or messages inside the cover image so that no one can access the actual data that is hidden inside the cover image.

In addition of providing the confidentiality authentication can also be provided by hiding the logo or thumbprint inside any jpeg image or document in jpeg format. The application can be extended by increasing the storage efficiency and hiding executable programs and allowing documents with other formats to be used in this application.

Limitations: The most obvious limitation to watermarking is that it can only be applied to bitmap images and the hiding mechanism requires that the cover image must be 8 times bigger than the watermark (either image or text).

Future Enhancements: There are several extensions to the concepts presented here such as increasing the storage efficiency and hiding executable programs in images.

The limitation to this application is that ratio of cover image to the watermark must be 8:1. This ratio can be reduced. Instead of using single least significant bit we can use 2 least significant bits of cover image for hiding watermark.

The other part of increasing the efficiency is to reduce the message image from eight-bit pixels to six-bit pixel. These six-bit pixel when hidden in 2 least significant bits of cover image can make the ratio fall down from 8:1 to 3:1.

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